

LARGE DEFLECTION CORRECTION FOR MODE II TOUGHNESS MEASUREMENT OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Large deflection response of the End-Loaded-Split (ELS) fracture test was analyzed by nonlinear beam theory. The effect of large deflection on measuring Mode II fracture toughness of composites was evaluated. The analysis was verified by testing PEEK/Carbon composite. Keywords: delamination, toughness, Mode II fracture, large deflection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mode II interlaminar toughness of fiber composites is commonly measured by subjecting cracked beam specimens to flexural tests [1]. The toughness is calculated from the linear elastic fracture mechanics relations:

$$G_c = \frac{P_{cr}^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

or

$$G_c = \frac{1}{2b} \frac{\delta_{cr}^2}{C^2} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (2)$$

where P_{cr} and δ_{cr} are respectively the load and deflection at fracture, a is the crack length and b is the uniform width of the beam. The flexural compliance C is often derived from linear beam theory. For the so-called End-Loaded-Split (ELS) fracture test [2] (Fig. 1a), for example, the Mode II toughness, G_{IIc} , is determined as

$$G_{IIc}(P) = \frac{18P_{cr}^2 a^2}{b^2 h^3 E_f} \quad (3)$$

or equivalently

$$G_{IIc}(\delta) = \frac{9\delta_{cr}^2 a^2 h^3 E_f}{8(3a^3 + L^3)^2} \quad (4)$$

where L is the span of the specimen, E_f is the flexural modulus and h is the total thickness of the beam. It is assumed in Eqs. 1 to 4 that the load-deflection (P - δ) response of the specimen is linear up to fracture. This requirement, however, may not always be satisfied. In testing composites with a higher toughness, a large deflection may be required to initiate the delamination. In such cases, G_{IIc} could still be calculated from linear beam theory. However the resulting values may not be accurate because the fracture occurs in the nonlinear range of the P - δ curve. Such effects could be minimized by increasing the sample thickness, while it is of

practical significance to evaluate the effect of large deflection and to provide corrections to the linear theory results.

Nonlinearity in the P - δ response may also be caused by plastic deformation at the crack tip and some stable growth of the possibly non-uniform crack front [3-5]. These mechanisms, coupled with the large deflection effect, often make it difficult to determine the actual crack length at which the fracture occurs. The difficulty is more pronounced in measuring the fracture resistance curve (the R -curve), where the load and deflection during crack growth could be measured while the corresponding crack length is unknown. Extension of the Mode II crack is hard to monitor from the specimen edges. If the plastic deformation is localized at the crack tip [4], the associated energy dissipation may be considered as part of the material resistance. This suggests that an effective crack length, a_{eff} , may be used to calculate the toughness. The value of a_{eff} may be determined from the measured load and deflection, and this requires that the sample response must be predicted for any crack length.

Large deflection response of the Double-Cantilever-Beam (DCB) Mode I fracture test has been studied in [6, 7]. The large deflection effect on Mode II toughness measurement using the End-Notched-Flexure (ENF) specimen, which is a cracked beam under three-point bending, was also studied in [8] by finite element method for a few typical crack sizes. Williams [7, 9] conducted large deflection analysis of the ELS fracture test, and the correction to Eq. 3 was given for two limiting cases: $dL \rightarrow 0$ and $dL \rightarrow 1$. The correction for other crack lengths was not obtained in [7, 9]. It is also noted that the ELS specimen in [7, 9] is modified from the DCB test, in which the load is applied to an end-block that is fixed to the beam surface. The modified ELS test (Fig. 1c) is not easy to implement in practice because, to maintain the vertical load, the distance between the load line and the clamped end should change during testing as the sample deflects. This is illustrated in Fig. 1c. In the original ELS test (Fig. 1a), the load nose may slide at the beam surface. Such a difference in test arrangement may result in different sample responses. In this work, the large deflection response of the original ELS test (Fig. 1a) was analyzed and the correction to toughness measurement was obtained for all range of crack lengths. The analysis was verified by testing the PEEK/Carbon thermoplastic composite APC-2.

2. LARGE DEFLECTION ANALYSIS

The original ELS specimen in Fig. 1a consists of three parts: the cracked parts (Beams 1 and 2) and the uncracked part (Beam 3). The sample geometry after deformation is shown in Fig. 1b. Denoting the beam deflection as v and assuming the coordinate system shown, the boundary conditions of the deflected specimen can be specified as follows. At the load point (Point A),

$$x=0, S=0, \varphi=\alpha \text{ and } v=\delta \quad (5)$$

at the crack tip (Point B),

$$x=l, S=a_1, \varphi=\alpha_1 \text{ and } v=\delta_1 \quad (6)$$

and at the clamped end (Point C),

$$x=L, S=L+(a_1-a), \varphi=0 \text{ and } v=0 \quad (7)$$

where a_1 is the current crack length, l is the horizontal distance from the load line to the crack tip and δ is the load-point deflection. Neglecting the friction between the load nose and the beam surface, load P acts normally to the contact point. The total bending moment M can be expressed as

$$M(x) = -P[x \cos \alpha + (\delta - v) \sin \alpha] \quad (8)$$

In the uncracked part: $M_3 = M$, and in the cracked parts: $M_1 = M_2 = M/2$.

Assuming a linear elastic stress-strain relation, the elementary beam equation holds

$$\frac{1}{R} = \frac{M}{E_f I} \quad (9)$$

where R is the radius of curvature of the deflected beam and I is the area moment of inertia of the uncracked beam section ($I = bh^3/12$). Eq. 9 is nonlinear in the range of large deflections. It may be solved by the procedure suggested in [7]. It is found that

$$a_1 = \sqrt{\frac{E_f I}{8P}} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \frac{d\varphi}{\sqrt{\sin(\alpha - \varphi)}} \quad (10)$$

$$l = \sqrt{\frac{E_f I}{8P}} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \frac{\cos\varphi d\varphi}{\sqrt{\sin(\alpha - \varphi)}} \quad (11)$$

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2E_f I}{P}} \int_0^{\alpha_1} \frac{\sin\varphi d\varphi}{\sqrt{4\sin(\alpha - \varphi) - 3\sin(\alpha - \alpha_1)}} + \sqrt{\frac{E_f I}{8P}} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \frac{\sin\varphi d\varphi}{\sqrt{\sin(\alpha - \varphi)}} \quad (12)$$

and, for a given α , P and α_1 are determined by the following equations:

$$L - a = \sqrt{\frac{2E_f I}{P}} \int_0^{\alpha_1} \frac{d\varphi}{\sqrt{4\sin(\alpha - \varphi) - 3\sin(\alpha - \alpha_1)}} \quad (13)$$

$$L = \sqrt{\frac{2E_f I}{P}} \int_0^{\alpha_1} \frac{\cos\varphi d\varphi}{\sqrt{4\sin(\alpha - \varphi) - 3\sin(\alpha - \alpha_1)}} + \sqrt{\frac{E_f I}{8P}} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \frac{\cos\varphi d\varphi}{\sqrt{\sin(\alpha - \varphi)}} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 2 shows the load-deflection response of a specimen with $a/L = 0.625$, where the load is normalized by $(L^2/E_f I)$ and the deflection by L . The response is linear at small deflections and it gradually becomes nonlinear as the deflection increases. Fig. 3 shows the current crack length a_1 as a function of the deflection. The crack length, and thus the beam length under load, increases with increasing deflection. The variation of a_1/a also depends on the initial crack length.

3. STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE

The strain energy release rate of a cracked beam may be determined by differentiating the strain energy U with respect to crack length a at a fixed deflection [9]. For the Mode II fracture test,

$$G_{II} = -\frac{1}{b} \frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \quad (\delta = \text{const}) \approx -\frac{1}{b} \frac{U(a + \Delta a) - U(a)}{\Delta a} \quad (\delta = \text{const}) \quad (15)$$

The differentiation was carried out numerically by evaluating the increment in U associated with a crack extension Δa . An increment of $\Delta a = 0.0001a$ was found to give convergent results.

Fig. 4 compares G_{II} by nonlinear beam theory to that by linear beam theory for the case of $a/L = 0.5$. Generally, for $a/L > 0.3$, G_{II} is underestimated by Eq. 3 and is overestimated by Eq. 4, whereas for shorter crack lengths, linear theory underestimates G_{II} using both Eqs. 3 and 4. To eliminate the large deflection effect, corrections to Eqs. 3 and 4 may be defined respectively as

$$F_P = \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}(P)} \quad (16)$$

and

$$F_{\delta} = \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}(\delta)} \quad (17)$$

The correction factors F_P and F_{δ} are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 respectively as functions of deflection for different crack lengths.

4. EXPERIMENT

Unidirectional ELS specimens [0]₂₀, $145 \times 12.5 \times 2.6$ mm, were manufactured from PEEK/Carbon APC-2 prepreg tape. The delamination was made by inserting a 25 μ m-thick

Kapton film during laying up. The fracture test was conducted on an Instron 1125 tester at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. The beam span was 80 mm and different crack lengths were considered. In order to avoid the artificially high value of Mode II toughness caused by the resin-rich region at the Kapton-film crack tip, Mode II precrack was produced as suggested in [3-5]. For precracking, the specimen was clamped with $a/L > 0.65$ and was loaded until the crack stably extended for about 10 mm. Some non-cracked specimens were also tested to measure the flexural modulus E_f following the procedure suggested in [10]. E_f was found to be about 115 GPa.

It has been noted in the previous discussions that, in the modified ELS test, the load remains vertical and the beam length constant during the sample deflection. In the original ELS test, on the other hand, the loading direction varies, remaining perpendicular to the beam axis, and the beam length increases as the sample deflects. In order to reveal the effects of such differences, the large deflection responses of non-cracked beams were studied and are compared in Fig. 7. It is seen that the response measured on the original ELS test could be well predicted by the previous analysis assuming zero crack length. The response under the modified test with a vertical load and a fixed beam length is identical to that of one arm of the DCB test as studied in [6, 7]. It agrees with that of the original test for small deflections but deviates significantly in the range of large deflections. If the beam length in the modified test is presumably varied as predicted in the original test at given deflections, the response still deviates from that of the original test in the large deflection range. Actually, only when both the increasing beam length and the varying loading direction were simulated in the modified test, did the responses of the two tests agree. This demonstrates the importance of formulating both the increasing beam length and varying loading direction in the large deflection analysis of the original ELS test.

Fig. 8 shows typical P - δ curves of cracked specimens. In both the unstable (a) and stable (b) fracture cases, the responses are linear at small deflections and gradually become nonlinear as the deflection increases. The test data of Case (b) are also plotted in Fig. 2. Except near the maximum load, P_{max} , the test data agree closely with the predicted curve.

The test data in Fig. 2 deviate from the predicted curve when approaching P_{max} . Previous studies on Mode II fracture of APC-2 composite using the ENF test [3-5] have shown that nonlinearity in P - δ response may also be caused by plastic deformation at the crack tip and slow stable crack growth. During testing, a few specimens were selectively unloaded at different load levels. The specimen edges were then examined under a microscope for crack extension. The unloading points are illustrated in Fig. 8(b), where Point 1 is in the range of initial nonlinearity, Point 2 is located just before P_{max} , and Point 3 (obtained only for stable fracture) is when the load had reached P_{max} and began to flatten or to drop. It was found that, at the load levels defined by Points 1 and 2, the crack growth (if it existed) was not visible from the sample edges, but crack growth was always observed at Point 3. Judging from the agreement in Fig. 2 between the test data and the predicted curve in the initial range of nonlinearity, it seems that the initial nonlinearity is due to the large deflection effect. The additional nonlinearity before P_{max} might be caused by material yielding at the crack tip and some stable growth of the non-uniform crack front inside the specimen [3-5]. In the present study, we took P_{max} as the load at crack initiation. The corresponding deflection is denoted as δ_{pmax} .

Based on the large deflection response predicted for any crack length, the effective crack length, a_{eff} , could be determined from (P_{max}, δ_{pmax}) . For the specimens tested, a_{eff} is typically 1 to 3 mm longer than the measured crack length. Table 1 compares the initiation toughness values calculated by linear beam theory and that after large deflection correction. G_{IIc} is underestimated by Eq. 3 and is overestimated by Eq. 4. The value after correction is close to that reported in [4, 5].

5. CONCLUSION

Large deflection response and its effect on Mode II toughness measurement are evaluated for any crack length for the End-Loaded-Split (ELS) fracture test. The toughness calculated by linear beam theory may be corrected by the correction factors provided in the present study.

6. REFERENCE

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Figure 1 End-loaded-split (ELS) fracture test: (a) original test [2], before deformation; (b) original test, after deformation; (c) modified ELS test [7, 9].

Figure 2
Load-deflection response of original ELS specimen ($a/L = 0.625$).

Figure 3
Current crack length (from load point to crack tip at deflected configuration) as a function of specimen deflection.

Figure 4
Comparison of strain energy release rates in ELS specimen calculated by linear and non-linear beam theories ($a/L = 0.5$).

Figure 5 Large-deflection correction factor for Mode II fracture toughness: F_P vs normalized deflection.

Figure 6 Large-deflection correction factor for Mode II fracture toughness: F_δ vs normalized deflection.

Figure 7 Comparison of large deflection responses of a non-cracked beam under the original and modified ELS tests.

Figure 8 Load-deflection response of PEEK/Carbon (APC-2) composite under ELS test: (a) unstable fracture; (b) stable fracture.

Table 1. Mode II initiation toughness of APC-2 composite.

Linear beam theory		Nonlinear beam theory
Eq. 3	Eq. 4	
2.07	3.40	2.32

FIRE RESISTANCE

